

Modeling and Analyzing Planning-Aware Distributed Cyber-Physical Systems with Timed Graph Transformation Systems

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Abstract. Distributed Cyber-Physical Systems are often safety-critical and, therefore, establishing their safety is of paramount importance. High-level models like timed graph transformation systems have been developed to cover the complex context-aware and self-aware behavior formally and enable to often verify safety at this level. To cover the communication delays inherent in Distributed Cyber-Physical Systems, also adding delay-robustness to these models has been studied. However, ensuring safety by design is often in conflict with other relevant goals like, for example, high throughput, as oftentimes the need for a delay-robust design leads to an overcautious behavior. By incorporating planning-awareness into the design such that Distributed Cyber-Physical Systems agents share their planning information, one can avoid the need to sacrifice throughput to ensure safety, compared to a design that is limited to context and self-awareness alone.

In this paper, we develop an approach employing timed graph transformation systems for Distributed Cyber-Physical Systems (i) to model planning-awareness without compromising verifiability, (ii) to derive such a model systematically from a non-planning-aware model, and (iii) to analyze for the derived model whether it compromises throughput to establish safety less often than the employed non-planning-aware model. As a running example, we consider a Distributed Cyber-Physical Systems in which multiple autonomous shuttles locally coordinate their movement on a track topology to avoid collisions while maximizing throughput.

Keywords: Cyber-Physical Systems · Model-driven Systems Engineering · Planning-Awareness · Delay-Robustness

1 Introduction

For safety-critical **Distributed Cyber-Physical Systems** (DCPS), it is of paramount importance to ensure safe operation. High-level modeling formalisms have been developed to formally capture complex context-aware and self-aware behaviors, and they often allow verifying safety properties at this level of abstraction (see [2, 18, 17, 29] among others).

To account for the communication delays inherent in DCPS, arising from transmission, propagation, queuing, and processing times (cf. [13, 40]), the addition of *delay robustness* to such models has also been investigated [16, 15]. Delays in inter-agent communication may cause agents to form incorrect assumptions about information received from others. In safety-critical environments, delayed messages may result in inaccurate estimates of other agents' positions, thereby increasing the risk of safety violations. Consequently, DCPS models must explicitly distinguish between local, immediate observations (occurring with zero delay) and remote, δ -delayed observations (subject to delays of up to δ time units). A system model is then considered *δ -delay robust* if it remains safe and functional even when remote observations are delayed by up to δ time units.

The authors proposed an approach for deriving δ -delay robust models from given zero-delay models in [16]. However, ensuring safety by design often conflicts with other key objectives such as maintaining high throughput, as achieving delay robustness frequently results in overcautious system behavior. In this mentioned approach, for example, safety reactions must be triggered whenever a potential future unsafe state cannot be excluded under all possible behaviors. Consequently, agents must take premature safety measures and halt operation to avoid potential unsafe states, leading to a reduction in throughput.

To address this limitation, we propose a planning-aware modeling approach in which agents share their planned future steps. This additional information allows agents to maintain safety without compromising throughput, outperforming purely context- and self-aware designs. Specifically, each agent is required to plan its next n steps in advance, covering at least Δ time units, where $\Delta > \delta$, and to communicate this plan to other agents, enabling them to coordinate their behavior accordingly. Even if parts of the exchanged plans are delayed by up to δ time units, agents can still make less overcautious decisions because reliable information remains available for at least $\Delta - \delta$ time units.

We developed this approach using *Timed Graph Transformation Systems (TGTSs)* [32], an extension of *Graph Transformation Systems (GTSs)* [12], to model planning-aware designs for DCPS. GTSs provide a powerful modeling formalism for systems whose states can be represented as graphs and whose state transitions are described by rule-based graph transformations. By integrating timing constraints such as clocks, guards, invariants, and resets, TGTSs offer a suitable framework for formally modeling autonomous agents in DCPS. Moreover, by encoding the agents' context within the graph and allowing rules to access not only local information but also contextual and other agents' states, TGTSs enable the formal specification of complex context-aware and self-aware behaviors under a non-zero-delay assumption [18]. To model planning-aware agents, the agents' next n steps are incorporated into the overall graph, allowing other agents to observe them as well. To this end, we propose an algorithm that determines the minimal required length n of the planning horizon. In particular, our presented approach supports

- (i) modeling planning-aware DCPS without compromising verifiability,
- (ii) deriving a planning-aware model with a corresponding planning horizon sys-

tematically from a non-planning-aware model, and (iii) analyzing for the derived model whether it compromises throughput to establish safety less often than the employed non-planning-aware model.

As a running example, we consider a DCPS in which multiple autonomous shuttles locally coordinate their movement on a shared track topology to avoid collisions. Our goal is to maximize throughput (i.e., to minimize braking) while ensuring that all shuttles safely reach their terminal tracks. To highlight our approach and simplify the exposition, we focus on a core behavioral and interaction pattern in which two shuttles independently approach a shared track segment from different predecessor tracks. We demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach through a series of experiments using various track topologies.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 establish the necessary foundations. In Section 3, we present our main contributions to model planning-aware designs without compromising verifiability (see Section 3.2), to derive most of such a model for a planning-aware designs systematically from a non-planning-aware model (see Section 3.3), and to analyze for the derived model whether it less often compromise throughput to establish safety than the employed not planning-aware model (see Section 4). Section 5 discusses related work, positioning our approach within the broader research landscape. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines potential directions for future research.

2 Background

We employ typed attributed graphs (graphs) [12] and injective graph morphism $m : G_1 \hookrightarrow G_2$ between them. For our running example, we rely on the type graph TG (see Figure 1a and the Start Graph G_0 from Figure 4). Here and subsequently, we use an abbreviated notation for graphs in which (a) node types are indicated by the node names (S , T , and M indicating shuttles, tracks, and markers (whose purpose we explain in the next section)), (b) edge types are omitted as edge types can be derived uniquely for TG, (c) node attributes and their values are, if present, given behind the node name (e.g., $S_1(c1, drive)$ in G_0 is a shuttle node with a *clock* attribute $c1$ of unspecified value and *mode* attribute of value *drive*).

Following the Double Pushout (DPO) approach in [12], graph transformation (GT) steps are derived by applying GT rules $\rho = (\ell : K \hookrightarrow L, r : K \hookrightarrow R)$ (where we assume ℓ and r to be inclusions) for a match $m : L \hookrightarrow G_1$. The morphisms ℓ and r capture elements to be preserved in K , deleted in $L - \ell(K)$, and created in $R - r(K)$. When depicting GT rules as in Figure 1b, we use a standard integrated notation for ℓ and r , providing a single graph where \ominus and \oplus indicate the elements to be deleted and created. As in Figure 2a, we depict the change of an attribute as $v1 \rightsquigarrow v2$ for values $v1$ and $v2$.

TGTs employ clocks and clock constraints (CCs) thereon. For a set of clock variables C , CCs $\psi \in \mathbf{CC}(C)$ are finite conjunctions of clock comparisons of the form $c1 \sim r$ and $c1 - c2 \sim r$ where $c1, c2 \in C$, $\sim \in \{<, >, \leq, \geq\}$, and $r \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{\infty\}$. Clock valuations $cv : C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ satisfy CCs ψ , written $cv \models \psi$, as expected.

Fig. 1. TGTS Type Graph TG and TGTS Rule driveD

For a clock valuation cv and a set of clocks C' , $cv[C' := 0]$ is the clock valuation mapping the clocks from C' to 0 and all other clocks according to cv . For a clock valuation cv and a duration $\delta \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$, $cv + \delta$ is the clock valuation mapping each clock x to $cv(x) + \delta$. We now discuss the syntax and semantics of TGTS with agent-based priorities, and present the TGTS model of our running example based on clock-based timing constraints. Each TGTS employs a type graph and contains a single start graph (for our running example, see again Figure 1a for TG and Figure 4 for G_0). In our running example, shuttles S_1 and S_2 are initially in mode *drive* and will advance on the track topology. TGTSs identify for each graph G a set of clock attributes $CA(G)$.

For our running example, these are the *clock* attributes of shuttle and marker nodes. TGTS states (G, cv) contain a graph G and for the clocks $CA(G)$ of G , a clock valuation $cv : CA(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$. The start state of a TGTS consists of the start graph and the clock valuation mapping all clocks to 0. TGTS invariants (I, ψ) contain a graph I and a CC $\psi \in \mathbf{CC}(CA(I))$. They are used to state clock constraints based on graph patterns that must be satisfied by all traversable TGTS states. A TGTS state (G, cv) satisfies a TGTS invariant (I, ψ) , if $cv \circ m \models \psi$ for every match $m : I \hookrightarrow G$. TGTS Atomic Propositions (AP) are given by graphs; each TGTS state (G, cv) is labeled with the TGTS AP A for which a match $m : A \rightarrow G$ exists.

In our running example, we employ the TGTS AP from Figure 2b capturing states, where two shuttles are located on a common track. The shuttles' clocks are reset to 0 upon each advancement and the TGTS invariant then prevents timed steps when a shuttle in mode *drive* has a clock value of 4 time units, capturing that such a shuttle must advance.

TGTS rules describe how discrete steps between TGTS states are to be derived. Rules $\sigma = (\rho, a, \psi, CR, p)$ consist of a GT rule $\rho = (\ell : K \hookrightarrow L, r : K \hookrightarrow R)$, an actor embedding $a : A \hookrightarrow L$, a clock guard $\psi \in \mathbf{CC}(CA(L))$ over the clocks of L , a reset set $CR \subseteq CA(R)$ of clocks to be reset, and a priority $p \in \mathbb{N}$.

For our running example, see Figure 1b, Figure 2a, Figure 3a, and Figure 3b for the visualizations of the rules employed where we depict the actor subgraph A (consisting of a shuttle node with its attributes each time) using a red, dashed

Fig. 2. TGTS Rule brake1D and TGTS AP Collision

border: Rule driveD represents the advancement of a shuttle from Track T_1 to T_2 after at least 3 time units. Rule brake1D, brake2D, and brake3D change the mode from *drive* to *brake* to avoid potential subsequent collision with a potential nearby shuttle with varying distances.

Fig. 3. TGTS Rule brake2D and brake3D

We refer to the local agent-based priority concept proposed in [16]. The standard GT rule priority concept is insufficient for TGTS modeling multi-agent systems because a high priority step s_1 for an actor A_1 prevents a lower priority step s_2 of another actor A_2 , which can lead to the modeling error of timelocks when A_2 must perform s_2 before A_1 can perform s_1 (for our running example, a shuttle that needs to brake using the brake rule prevents a step using drive to be executed by all other shuttles). To evaluate priorities for agents separately, we rely on the actor embedding $a : A \hookrightarrow L$ in the rules. Local agent-based priorities can be encoded using application conditions.

A TGTS $S = (G_0, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{AP})$ consists of a start graph G_0 , a set of rules \mathcal{P} , a set of TGTS invariants \mathcal{I} , and a set of TGTS AP \mathcal{AP} . For such a TGTS S , we use TGTS $states(S)$ to capture its TGTS states satisfying all its TGTS invariants \mathcal{I} .

The single step relation of a TGTS S on TGTS states (G, cv) defines timed steps in which time elapses by adding the same delay to all clocks requiring that the implicitly traversed steps are TGTS states as well, and discrete steps where

a rule is applied by applying its underlying GT rule and resetting the clocks in the reset set to 0 requiring that the clock guard of the rule is satisfied and that no rule of \mathcal{S} with an overlapping actor-embedding and higher priority is applicable. Consequently, the passage of time competes with possibly multiple rule applications of possibly multiple actors, resulting in non-determinism. Finally, we define the two types of steps of a TGTS.

Definition 1 (TGTS Steps). TGTS $S = (G_0, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{AP})$ defines a set of timed and discrete labeled steps $\text{steps}(S)$ among TGTS states of S .

- *Timed Step:* $((G_1, cv_1), \delta, (G_1, cv_1 + \delta)) \in \text{steps}(S)$ if $(G_1, cv_1) \in \text{states}(S)$, $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^+$, and $(G_1, cv_1 + \delta') \in \text{states}(S)$ for each delay $\delta' \in [0, \delta]$.
- *Discrete Step:* $((G_1, cv_1), (\sigma, m), (G_2, cv_2)) \in \text{steps}(S)$ if $(G_1, cv_1), (G_2, cv_2) \in \text{states}(S)$, $\sigma = (\rho, a : A \hookrightarrow L, \psi, CR, p) \in \mathcal{P}$, $\rho = (\ell : K \hookrightarrow L, r : K \hookrightarrow R)$, $m : L \hookrightarrow G_1$ (match), $(G_1, (\rho, m, k, \bar{m}, \ell', r'), G_2) \in \text{GTsteps}$ (GT step), $cv_1 \models \psi$ (clock guard satisfaction), $cv_2 = cv_1[\bar{m}(CR) := 0]$ (reset of clocks), and $\nexists \sigma' = (\rho', a' : A' \hookrightarrow L', \psi', CR', p') \in \mathcal{P}$ $((G_1, cv_1), (\sigma', m'), _) \in \text{steps}(S) \wedge (m \circ a)(A)$ and $(m' \circ a')(A')$ overlap $\wedge p' > p$ (priorities).

The states of the (forward constructed) symbolic state space are of the form (G, ψ) representing TGTS states (G, cv) where $cv \models \psi$. The syntactic restrictions of CCs are sufficient to ensure the finiteness of the symbolic state space when a finite number of discrete state components can be reached.

3 Modeling

3.1 Problem Statement

As demonstrated by our previous work [16], the presence of δ -delayed inter-agent messages disrupts synchronization among agents within a multi-agent system, as agents may base their decisions on outdated information. Such synchronization disruptions pose significant risks to the system's safety requirements. To address this problem, the authors proposed a methodology to derive TGTS rules that guarantee robustness with respect to δ -delayed messages (with $\delta = 1$ time unit, an assumption we also adopt in this paper) while ensuring safety. However, this approach tends to result in overcautious configurations, consequently restricting overall system efficiency by limiting throughput. In this section, we illustrate the limitations of their approach through their provided running example. The example involves multiple autonomous shuttles that locally coordinate their movements on a shared track topology. See Figure 4 for the topology, and Figures 1b, 2a, 3a, 3b for the corresponding TGTS rule set, which we denote as *Comparison Model*, in short: CM.

In [16], we considered the track topology without the green labeled tracks (i.e., excluding tracks T_7 and T_G). Consider the initial state of this topology, where S_1 is at T_1 , and S_2 at T_A . Moreover, we consider T_F as a potential conflict track since the location of two shuttles at this track simultaneously leads to a collision. (Recall that we consider a collision (see Figure 2b) as a safety violation.)

Fig. 4. TGTS Start Graph G_0

The application of their proposed solution (i.e., CM) to this topology leads to a state in which shuttle S_1 terminates at T_6 and S_2 at T_E . This is realized since S_1 brakes at T_5 and S_2 brakes at T_D to avoid a collision at T_F .

However, if we consider the topology with the green labeled tracks (called extended topology), then the application of CM causes both shuttles to brake for every trace of this model. This also holds if S_1 aims to traverse track T_7 instead of T_F , where a collision is obviously not possible because both shuttles are not located at a common track at the same time since they do not share a common track, and, thus, safety is preserved. Hence, due to overcautious braking behavior, the shuttles of CM brake in every trace for this given topology. We consider this behavior as a throughput limitation. To address this limitation, we propose an approach (see Section 3.2) to minimize braking. We employ the running example of CM to ease comparison between the two solutions.

3.2 Planning-Aware DCPS Models

In this section, we introduce the notion of planning awareness for DCPS models. Such models are characterized by the explicit integration of an agent's planned steps. In the following, we formally define a planned state and a planned step, and illustrate their application using our running example.

Definition 2 (Planned State). *A planned TGTS state ps consists of $graph(ps)$, which is the planned graph, which contains all present and planned graph elements. Moreover, $v(ps): graph(ps) \rightarrow \mathbf{R}_0^+$ is the current valuation of all present and planned graph clocks.*

Definition 3 (Planned Step).

- *Timed Step:* Let $[ts] = (G_c, v_c)$ with $v_c = v(ps)$. Then, $([ts], \theta + v_c, [ts]')$ is a planned timed TGTS step, where $\theta \in \mathbf{R}_0^+$ models the elapse of time.
- *Discrete Step:* Let $[ds] = (G_p, v_p)$ with $v_p = v(ps)$. Let $(\sigma = (\rho, a : A \hookrightarrow L, \psi, CR, p) \in \mathcal{P}, \rho = (\ell : K \hookrightarrow L, r : K \hookrightarrow R), m : L \hookrightarrow G_1$ (match)) according to Definition 1. Then, $(ds, \delta + v_p, \sigma, ds')$ is a planned discrete TGTS step.

In general, we create a planning-aware model (PM) based on our algorithm (see Section 3.3) that takes as input a non-planning-aware model. The algorithm computes the planning horizon length for a given TGTS rule. Thus, a planning-aware TGTS rule is formed by the integration of a planning horizon into a non-planning-aware TGTS rule.

To construct the PM for our running example, we revisit CM, which serves as input to derive the planning horizon. By integrating the derived planning horizon into CM, we obtain PM. (Recall, CM is the solution proposed in [16].)

The `createPlan` rule (see Figure 5) with priority 1 represent the notion of a planning rule, where shuttle S_1 marks track segment T_2 and marks by the application of the rule T_3 as the planned step while its mode remains in *drive*. Its application is independent of clock valuations and depends exclusively on the current graph structure. Consequently, it uses an unconditional guard (i.e., Guard: true) and involves no invariants or clock resets. Intuitively, the `createPlan` rule is enabled as soon as an agent is connected by a directed edge to exactly one marker node. Once enabled, it is immediately applied (i.e., without any time elapse), linking the existing marker node to the newly generated marker node via a directed edge, thereby maintaining the planning horizon of two (which we describe in Section 3.3).

The PM of our running example incorporates the TGTS rules *brakeR*, *driveR*, and *createPlan* (see Figure 6b, 6a, and 5). Recall, we construct *driveR* and *brakeR* based on the *brake1D* (see Figure 2a) and *driveD* (see Figure 1b) automatically by means of our proposed algorithm, which equips each shuttle with two marker nodes representing its planning horizon.

Rule *driveR* (see Figure 6a) ensures the movement of a shuttle from the currently located track to the next track. The application of this rule deletes the marker node of the target track, while it creates an edge to the marker node of the next track.

Fig. 5. TGTS Rule `createPlan`

Rule *brakeR* (see Figure 6b) changes the mode of a shuttle from *drive* to *brake* since T_3 is marked by the marker node M_2 of a remote agent. This is visible due to the existence of M_2 without an incoming edge from M_1 . Rule *brakeR* ensures

Fig. 6. TGTS Rule driveR and brakeR

the advancement from the current location to the next track, where the last marker node M_1 of S_1 is located. Moreover, it deletes this marker node located at the targeted track and causes the shuttle to terminate at the newly occupied track (i.e., T_2). The application of the TGTS rule `createPlan` (see Figure 5) generates an additional marker node representing the step after next. Note, the `createPlan` rule generates a marker node with a corresponding edge from the existing marker node during execution. This rule ensures that each shuttle is equipped with marker nodes permanently.

The generic scheme for deriving TGTS rules for PM is as follows. We extract the behavioural model of PM from the behavioural model of CM. We then integrate a planning horizon into PM so that it captures not only the current but also the planned behaviour. This is achieved by introducing a planning horizon via a corresponding TGTS rule, which ensures that the length of the planning horizon remains constant. Since collisions are guaranteed not to occur in PM, we exploit this property by executing PM through CM.

In the following, we use the tool [22] to simulate situations using PM. To this end, we employ the extended topology of Figure 7. Consider for the initial state S_1 with $M_{1,1}$ and $M_{1,2}$ indicating the traversal of T_2 and T_3 , while S_2 with $M_{2,1}$ and $M_{2,2}$ for the traversal of T_B and T_C . Note, for brevity, we omit the TGTS rule for the generation of the two initial planning nodes for each agent. For the same reason, we omit the visualization of (a) clock attributes from the marker nodes and (b) the δ -delayed inter-agent message passing.

We now discuss Situation 1, where we construct a planning conflict, i.e., two agents intend to mark a common location at the same time leading potentially to an unsafe state.

Situation 1: Both Shuttles plan to traverse the conflict track T_F at the same time Starting from this initial state, both shuttles traverse locations by processing their marked locations using the `driveR` rule and subsequently marking additional locations through the application of the `createPlan` rule, leading to the state depicted by Figure 8.

Assume S_1 marks T_F first. This leads to a planning conflict as S_2 intends to mark/ traverse this conflict track as well. Since S_1 marks this conflict track

Fig. 7. TGTS Extended Topology for PRTM with Initial State

Fig. 8. TGTS Extended Topology with S_1 on the verge to plan further steps leading to a potential conflict with S_2 at T_F

first implying that S_2 is not allowed to mark/ traverse that track, S_2 performs the rule `brakeR` to stop at T_E to avoid a collision. Recall that we assume for the running example an inter-agent message passing delay of up to one time unit (inherited from [16]). Therefore, S_1 is required to communicate its two planned steps (which includes the conflict point) while locating at T_5 , such that S_2 obtains this message (documenting the planned steps of S_1) during its stay at T_D .

As a result, S_2 performs `brakeR` at T_D to stop at T_E . Eventually, S_1 traverses the conflict point to terminate at T_G . Note if S_2 marks first the conflict track, then S_1 is not required to brake since T_7 is then an option to traverse while preserving the system safety.

Situation 2: One shuttle plans to traverse the conflict track T_F at a time Given Figure 8, if S_1 marks as next step T_7 , while locating at T_5 , then S_2 traverses T_F . Since S_1 transmits his remote plan at T_5 , S_2 obtains this message at the latest while located at T_D (due to the δ -delayed message exchange). Therefore, S_2 eventually traverse T_F and S_1 T_7 and both shuttles terminate at a terminal track without braking.

From these two situations, we conclude the following. In CM, both shuttles brake and terminate before reaching the terminal tracks. This also holds for Situation 2, where both shuttles intend to traverse different tracks and therefore a collision is not possible. Still, both shuttles brake and terminate before their desired terminal track. We consider this braking behavior as a limitation of throughput. This limitation occurs due to overcautious configurations to manage

delayed inter-agent messages while preserving safety, and resulting in reduced overall throughput. In contrast, by employing PM, either one shuttle or no shuttle brakes. Recall that we consider braking as limiting throughput.

3.3 Construction Scheme of Planning Horizon

In the previous section, we presented the notion of PM. In this section, we discuss Algorithm 1 to construct the planning horizon of a PM. Given the solution of CM (see Figures 1b, 2a, 3a, and 3b) as input, we calculate the length of the planning horizon using this algorithm.

To enable collaborative planning by means of a PM, an agent exchanges its remote plan with remote agents. In a remote plan, an agent documents its current location, fixates its planned steps, and shares this plan with remote agents. Once an agent processes a planned step, it updates and transmits its current remote plan, such that remote agents are informed regarding its updated planned steps, and updated location. If a location is marked (i.e., included in an agent’s remote plan), no other agent is permitted to mark or traverse this marked location. The traversal of a marked location is only permitted by an agent whose remote plan contains this marked location as a next immediate step. Therefore, remote agents are required to stop at the latest at the preceding location before reaching that marked location (or select another location to traverse if possible).

Given the inter-agent message delay (i.e., $\delta = 1$ time unit), parts of the remote plan may be outdated upon reception for remote agents since the message-sending agent may directly perform a step (i.e., change location) after sending his remote plan, which, as a result, incorrectly states the previous location as the latest one. Hence, the remote plan must contain the number of planned steps (i.e., planning horizon) such that parts of the remote plan are not outdated upon reception for the remote message-receiving agents to ensure collaboration. To address this, we quantify the number of steps of a remote plan may be become outdated.

In particular, we calculate the number of steps that are possible during δ -delayed messages. Then, we over-approximate (i.e., either round up or increase it by one) this number, which serves as the length of the planning horizon. By doing this, we ensure that parts of the remote plan are not outdated upon reception since the length of the planning horizon is greater than the number of possible steps during δ -delayed messages. Intuitively, agents must plan their planned steps such that at least Δ time units are covered and communicate this remote plan to remote agents. Given the remote plan, remote agents can coordinate their behavior based on the received information. Even when parts of the exchanged plans are delayed up to δ time units, remote agents can make less overcautious decisions as proper information for the next $\Delta - \delta$ time units is always available.

Algorithm 1 determines the length of the *Planning Horizon* (represented by the variable PH) based on the numerical value of *Guard* and *Invariant*. After computing $\text{temp} = \text{Invariant} - \text{Guard}$, four cases are identified to ensure that the length of the planning horizon is greater than the number of possible steps being

Algorithm 1 Calculation of the length of the Planning Horizon

Require: Guard, Invariant, $\delta = 1$. Precondition: $1 < \text{Guard} < \text{Invariant} \leq 15$.

Ensure: PH, where $2 \leq \text{PH} \leq 15$ represents the length of the Planning Horizon.

```

1: temp  $\leftarrow$  Invariant - Guard
2: if temp = Guard then
3:   PH  $\leftarrow$   $\delta + 1$ 
4: else if temp < Guard and temp =  $\delta$  then
5:   PH  $\leftarrow$   $\delta + 1$ 
6: else if temp > Guard then
7:   PH  $\leftarrow$   $\left\lceil \frac{\text{temp}}{\text{Guard}} \right\rceil$ 
8: else
9:   PH  $\leftarrow$   $\left\lceil \frac{\text{Invariant}}{\text{Guard}} \right\rceil$ 
10: end if
11: return PH

```

outdated in the remote plan. If $\text{temp} = \text{Guard}$, then it is possible that at most one step is outdated if this potentially outdated step happens immediately after being enabled due to $\text{temp} = \text{Guard}$ and $\text{Invariant} - \text{Guard} = \text{temp}$ causing inaccuracy in the remote plan. Therefore, PH is set to $\delta + 1$ to exceed the system delay ($\delta = 1$). If $\text{temp} < \text{Guard}$ and equals δ , then it is also possible to have a deviation of maximally one step if $(\text{temp} + \delta) = \text{Guard}$. Hence, PH is assigned $(\delta + 1)$. For $\text{temp} > \text{Guard}$, PH is computed by $\left\lceil \frac{\text{temp}}{\text{Guard}} \right\rceil$. Also, for $1 < \text{temp} < \text{Guard}$, PH is computed by $\left\lceil \frac{\text{Invariant}}{\text{Guard}} \right\rceil$. In both branches, we cover cases, where either temp or Invariant is many times greater than Guard. Therefore, we divide either temp or Invariant by Guard to calculate how many times the guard fits into temp or Invariant. To ensure $\Delta > \delta$, we round up the quotient, which we then use as (a bounded) length of the planning horizon.

Recent works in the field of motion planning [14, 23] assume a maximum of 15 steps as a planning horizon. Hence, while we require PH to be 15 at most, our objective is to compute the minimal required number for the planning horizon to ensure safety and throughput.

In the following, we apply the algorithm to our running example. Consider the case where $\text{Guard} = 3$ and $\text{Invariant} = 4$. (Recall, we inherited these valuations from CM.) First, we calculate temp: $\text{temp} = \text{Invariant} - \text{Guard} = 4 - 3 = 1$. Next, we check the conditions of the algorithm:

- $\text{temp} = \text{Guard}$ is false, since $1 \neq 3$.
- $\text{temp} < \text{Guard}$ and $\text{temp} = \delta = 1$ is true, because $1 < 3$ and $\delta = 1$.

Therefore, the second branch applies, we compute $\text{PH} = \text{temp} + 1 = 1 + 1 = 2$. Thus, for $\text{Guard} = 3$ and $\text{Invariant} = 4$, the length of the planning horizon is 2. During the transmission of a remote plan, a shuttle traverses one track segment at most due to the guard (= 3 time units) and invariant (= 4 time units) of the rules driveR and brakeR. This causes the location deviation in a remote plan

by one track segment exactly. To compensate for this deviation, we calculate a planning horizon of two track segments (by the operation $(\delta + 1)$, resulting in $\text{PH} = 2$) such that parts of the remote plan are not outdated upon reception. Therefore, we define two marker nodes, M_1 and M_2 , as the planning horizon in the running example.

In the following, we prove termination and correctness of our algorithm.

Theorem 1 (Termination). *The Planning Horizon Algorithm terminates for all inputs g and n satisfying $1 < g < n \leq 15$.*

Proof. The algorithm consists of a finite sequence of arithmetic operations and a fixed conditional (if-else) structure. It contains no loops or recursive calls. Consequently, for any valid input, the algorithm reaches its return statement after a finite number of steps. Therefore, the algorithm always terminates.

Theorem 2 (Correctness). *Let g and n be integers satisfying $1 < g < n \leq 15$, and set $\delta = 1$. Define $\text{temp} = n - g > 0$, and let PH be the value returned by the Planning Horizon Algorithm. Then*

$$\text{PH} = \max(2, \lceil \text{temp}/g \rceil).$$

Proof. The value of temp determines four mutually exclusive and exhaustive cases corresponding to the branches of the conditional structure.

(I) *Case $\text{temp} = g$.* The algorithm returns $\delta + 1 = 2$. Since $\text{temp}/g = 1$, we have $\lceil \text{temp}/g \rceil = 1$, and hence $\max(2, 1) = 2$.

(II) *Case $\text{temp} < g$ and $\text{temp} = \delta = 1$.* The algorithm returns $\text{temp} + 1 = 2$, which equals $\max(2, \lceil \text{temp}/g \rceil)$ because $0 < 1/g < 1$ implies $\lceil \text{temp}/g \rceil = 1$.

(III) *Case $\text{temp} > g$.* The algorithm returns $\lceil \text{temp}/g \rceil$. Since $\text{temp}/g > 1$, the ceiling value is at least 2, and therefore matches the formula.

(IV) *Case $1 < \text{temp} < g$.* Here $n = g + \text{temp}$ gives

$$1 + \frac{1}{g} < \frac{n}{g} < 2,$$

so $\lceil n/g \rceil = 2$. Moreover, $0 < \text{temp}/g < 1$ implies $\lceil \text{temp}/g \rceil = 1$, and thus $\max(2, 1) = 2$, which coincides with the algorithm's output.

These four cases cover all possibilities for $\text{temp} > 0$. In each case, the algorithm returns exactly $\max(2, \lceil \text{temp}/g \rceil)$. Therefore, the algorithm works correctly.

4 Evaluation

We evaluate our approach in an experimental setting regarding three different objectives. First, we evaluate whether our approach violates the safety-critical requirement. Then, we evaluate the throughput, and the scalability of our approach. The latter includes three further experiments, where we incrementally add two conflict tracks per experiment in the used topologies (see Figure 9).

This topology contains seven highlighted conflict points: T_F , T_7 , T_G , T_8 , T_H , T_9 , and T_I . For the second experiment (Exp2), we employ the topology without the tracks T_8 , T_H , T_9 , T_I . Hence, T_7 and T_G are the predecessor tracks of T_{10} and T_J . We extend the topology with track segments T_8 and T_H but still exclude T_9 and T_I for the second experiment (Exp3). Lastly, we extend this topology with track segments T_9 and T_I (Exp4). Track segments T_{10} and T_J have no impact, since they are not connected and are used solely for diagnostic purposes, as they are terminal tracks.

Fig. 9. TGTS Topology used for the Evaluation

Comparison Based on the given input model (i.e., CM), we automatically generated PM. Once we obtain PM, we conduct a series of Experiments (see results in Figure 11b): (a) We generate the state space of PM for all four topologies, and (b) we generate the state space of CM for all four topologies. To compute the state space for the above cases, we used Henshin [22]. For the state space generation of PM, we used the corresponding model PM. Similarly, for CM. We compared both state spaces in terms of identical traces (see Figure 10, which we used for the evaluation).

See Figure 11b for the effort invested in the state space generation for all experiments containing topologies (see Figure 7 and 9). Note that CM never traversed the first conflict track. Therefore, the state space remains similar to the first experiment (Exp1), see situations 1 and 2 of 3.2.

	PM	CM
Identical Trace	Number of Brakes	Number of Brakes
1	2	2
2	1	2
3	1	2
4	0	2
5	0	2

Fig. 10. Number of Brakes of PM and CM per identical Trace

Fig. 11. Experimental Results comparing Planning-aware Model (PM) and Comparison Model (CM)

Comparison of Results Both models, PM and CM, preserve safety based on our experiments. This can be checked in Henshin using AP collision (see Figure 2b) with the highest priority detecting a collision by marking configurations in the state space, where the AP can be matched. We observe that this AP labels no state. Moreover, we analyzed the state space through PRISM, a model checker tool [24], where safety and real-time behaviour are formally verified. Hence, no additional analysis is required, and safety is guaranteed.

CM exhibits overcautious behavior in scenarios where a collision may happen. Therefore, both shuttles always brake and terminate at T_6 and T_E . This also holds for the case where both shuttles aim to traverse different tracks (i.e., T_7 and T_G), in which a collision is not possible. Consequently, in each of its five traces, both shuttles of CM brake. Moreover, none of the seven highlighted conflict tracks were reached in any trace. As a result of this, the generated state space of CM remains unchanged and consists of 41 states with a state space effort of 11.8 seconds (see Figure 11b).

In comparison, while PM has a state space with 81 states and efforts of 15.3 seconds for its first experiment, it has 257 states with efforts of 32.1 seconds for the last experiment. PM exhibits different behavior in the context of the five identical traces. In two traces, one shuttle brakes, respectively. While in one trace both shuttles brake, in two remaining traces, neither shuttle brakes. An overview of the results is shown in Figure 10. Figure 11b illustrates the quantitative results of PM across four experiments. We conclude that PM outperforms CM since it minimizes braking while ensuring safety with manageable efforts under δ -delayed messages.

5 State-of-the-Art and Related Work

The idea of planning is not new. In the context of multi-agent systems, Daun et al. [10] proposed a framework where planning is realized through runtime models, based on individual agent goals.

A formal approach modeling the next immediate planned steps was introduced in [9]. The authors presented the Sonar-Formalism, based on Petri Nets, where distributed planning is implemented through "tasks." If two agents need to execute the same task, they synchronize their next intermediate steps. This approach restricts the planning horizon to a single next step.

Petri Nets, specifically fuzzy Petri Nets, were also employed in [8] to model sequence planning for a single agent robotic system guaranting preservation of properties such as safety.

Timed Automata have been applied to model multi-robot systems, as demonstrated in [34]. Here, collaboration is achieved via synchronization channels, and agents are constrained within a predefined movement radius represented as a planar grid.

Graph transformations have also been explored for architectural reconfiguration. In [38], the authors demonstrated how to transform graph transformation rules into actions for the Planning Domain Definition Language (PDDL), allowing off-the-shelf tools to compute self-adaptation plans.

In [20], the authors presented a different version of Timed Graph Transformation Systems not supporting quantitative analysis and not considering delay-robustness.

Another adaptation-based approach was presented in [26], where adaptation plans were derived based on a given system state model and a desired state model. These adaptation plans were then used to control the behavior of runtime models using the Unified Modeling Language [4].

Automated planning in the context of self-adaptive systems was proposed in [31]. The hybrid planning approach introduced in this work aims to balance potentially conflicting requirements of timeliness and optimality in adaptation plans.

Regarding the modeling of timing constraints, GTS have been extended to variations of TGTS in [19, 21, 33, 3, 35] without relying on clocks as in Timed Automata (TA) [1] and to variations based on clocks in [27, 28, 30]. Distribution aspects complicating design solutions as considered for our context in 3 have been surveyed in [15], and in [41] listing further aspects of general relevance.

Clock-related effects such as clock drifts and imprecise clock measurements (jittering) have been investigated thoroughly in the fundamental setting of TA [1] as surveyed in [5, 7, 6] but also for Hybrid Automata [37, 11, 39]. In particular, in [28] shuttle convoy establishment was analyzed where message delays have been implicitly considered (by limiting the number communications per time) in the context of probabilistic communication failures.

In [36, 25], similar examples on self-driving cars employing delayed unreliable wireless communication is considered where cars communicate information on

current or future locations and are manually designed at a concrete, explicit level to adjust information from received messages based on delay estimates.

In a discrete time setting, delay-robustness of timed distributed system has been investigated in [43] in the context of supervisory control theory.

Lastly, in [42] design-time and run-time analysis are integrated whereby symbolic paths to violations are derived (backwards as in k -induction) at design-time to increase the look-ahead towards such violations at run-time. However, this approach considers untimed systems and attempts to disable steps leading to unsafe states.

While these works contribute to planning and adaptation in distributed systems, they do not comprehensively integrate real-time constraints, such as inter-agent message passing delays and corresponding countermeasure techniques in safety-critical environments to maximize throughput. Our approach addresses this gap by introducing a framework that supports formal reasoning with a planning horizon algorithm tailored to multi-agent systems (such as DCPS) with δ -delayed message exchanges in real-time. Moreover, in this work, we benefit from modeling planning-aware designs without compromising verifiability. Thereby, we derive a planning-aware design systematically from a non-planning-aware model to ensure safety and maximize throughput.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

In this work, we addressed the challenge of ensuring safety in DCPS while avoiding throughput limitations caused by overcautious δ -delay-robust designs. We introduced a planning-aware modeling approach based on TGTS that enables agents to share their future plans to enhance coordination under δ -delayed messages. The presented algorithm determines the minimal required planning horizon length ensuring that sufficient future information is always available for remote agents to maintain safety, throughput, and verifiability. Already for our running example, we conclude that our automatic rule derivation approach can ease model-driven engineering for DCPS. As future work, we aim to extend our approach to more complex track topologies with more than two agents and varying delay conditions. To further enhance system adaptability, we plan to consider dynamic adjustments to planning horizons.

References

- [1] R. Alur and D. L. Dill. “A Theory of Timed Automata”. In: *Theor. Comput. Sci.* 126.2 (1994), pp. 183–235. DOI: [10.1016/0304-3975\(94\)90010-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3975(94)90010-8).
- [2] B. Becker, D. Beyer, H. Giese, F. Klein, and D. Schilling. “Symbolic invariant verification for systems with dynamic structural adaptation”. In: *28th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE 2006), Shanghai, China, May 20-28, 2006*. Ed. by L. J. Osterweil, H. D. Rombach, and M. L. Soffa. ACM, 2006, pp. 72–81. DOI: [10.1145/1134285.1134297](https://doi.org/10.1145/1134285.1134297).
- [3] B. Becker and H. Giese. “On Safe Service-Oriented Real-Time Coordination for Autonomous Vehicles”. In: *11th IEEE International Symposium on Object-Oriented Real-Time Distributed Computing (ISORC 2008), 5-7 May 2008, Orlando, Florida, USA*. IEEE Computer Society, 2008, pp. 203–210. ISBN: 978-0-7695-3132-8. DOI: [10.1109/ISORC.2008.13](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISORC.2008.13). URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/mostRecentIssue.jsp?punumber=4519543>.
- [4] G. Booch. *The unified modeling language user guide*. Pearson Education India, 2005.
- [5] P. Bouyer. “Timed automata”. In: *Handbook of Automata Theory*. Ed. by J. Pin. European Mathematical Society Publishing House, Zürich, Switzerland, 2021, pp. 1261–1294. DOI: [10.4171/Automata-2/12](https://doi.org/10.4171/Automata-2/12).
- [6] P. Bouyer, P. Gastin, F. Herbretreau, O. Sankur, and B. Srivathsan. “Zone-Based Verification of Timed Automata: Extrapolations, Simulations and What Next?” In: *FORMATS 2022*. Ed. by S. Bogomolov and D. Parker. Vol. 13465. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2022, pp. 16–42. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-15839-1_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-15839-1_2).
- [7] P. Bouyer, O. Kupferman, N. Markey, B. Maubert, A. Murano, and G. Perelli. “Reasoning about Quality and Fuzziness of Strategic Behaviours”. In: *IJCAI 2019*. Ed. by S. Kraus. ijcai.org, 2019, pp. 1588–1594. DOI: [10.24963/ijcai.2019/220](https://doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2019/220).
- [8] T. Cao and A. Sanderson. “Task sequence planning using fuzzy Petri nets”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics* 25.5 (1995), pp. 755–768. DOI: [10.1109/21.376489](https://doi.org/10.1109/21.376489).
- [9] L. Capra, M. Kohler-Bussmeier, H. Rolke, J. Sudeikat, et al. “Petri Nets as Run-Time Models for Self-Adaptive Cyber-Physical Systems Cost-Benefit Analysis of Structural Transformations”. In: *CEUR WORKSHOP PROCEEDINGS*. Vol. 3730. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. 2024, pp. 164–181.
- [10] M. Daun, V. Stenkova, L. Krajinski, J. Brings, T. Bandyszak, and T. Weyer. “Goal modeling for collaborative groups of cyber-physical systems with GRL: reflections on applicability and limitations based on two studies conducted in industry”. In: *Proceedings of the 34th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing* (2019). URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:142503523>.
- [11] B. Denis, J. Lesage, and Z. Juárez-Orozco. “Performance Verification of discrete Event Systems using Hybrid Model-Checking”. In: *ADHS 2006*. Ed. by C. G. Cassandras, A. Giua, C. Seatzu, and J. Zaytoon. Vol. 39. IFAC Proceedings Volumes 5. Elsevier, 2006, pp. 365–370. DOI: [10.3182/20060607-3-IT-3902.00067](https://doi.org/10.3182/20060607-3-IT-3902.00067).
- [12] H. Ehrig, K. Ehrig, U. Prange, and G. Taentzer. “Fundamentals of Algebraic Graph Transformation. 2006”. In: *EATCS Monographs in Theoretical Computer Science* (2006).
- [13] B. A. Forouzan. *Data communications and networking*. Huga Media, 2007.

- [14] A. Gautam, Y. He, and X. Lin. “Motion Planning for Autonomous Driving in Unsignalized Intersections Using Combined Multi-Modal GNN Predictor and MPC Planner”. In: *Machines* 13.9 (2025). DOI: [10.3390/machines13090760](https://doi.org/10.3390/machines13090760).
- [15] M. Ghani and H. Giese. “Towards Model Consistency between abstract and explicit Delay-Robustness in Timed Graph Transformation System”. In: *ZEUS 2025* (2025), p. 12.
- [16] M. Ghani, S. Schneider, M. Maximova, and H. Giese. “Deriving Delay-Robust Timed Graph Transformation System Models”. In: *International Conference on Graph Transformation*. Springer. 2024, pp. 158–179.
- [17] H. Giese. “Formal Models and Analysis for Self-adaptive Cyber-physical Systems”. In: *Formal Aspects of Component Software*. Ed. by O. Kouchnarenko and R. Khosravi. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017, pp. 3–9.
- [18] H. Giese, T. Vogel, and S. Wätzoldt. “Towards Smart Systems of Systems”. In: *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Fundamentals of Software Engineering (FSEN '15)*. Ed. by M. Dastani and M. Sirjani. Vol. 9392. Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS). (invited paper). Springer, 2015, pp. 1–29. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-24644-4_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24644-4_1).
- [19] S. Gyapay, R. Heckel, and D. Varró. “Graph Transformation with Time: Causality and Logical Clocks”. In: *ICGT 2002*. Ed. by A. Corradini, H. Ehrig, H. Kreowski, and G. Rozenberg. Vol. 2505. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2002, pp. 120–134. DOI: [10.1007/3-540-45832-8_11](https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-45832-8_11).
- [20] S. Gyapay, R. Heckel, and D. Varró. “Graph transformation with time: Causality and logical clocks”. In: *Graph Transformation: First International Conference, ICGT 2002 Barcelona, Spain, October 7–12, 2002 Proceedings 1*. Springer. 2002, pp. 120–134.
- [21] S. Gyapay, D. Varró, and R. Heckel. “Graph Transformation with Time”. In: *Fundam. Inform.* 58.1 (2003), pp. 1–22. URL: <https://content.iospress.com/articles/fundamenta-informaticae/fi58-1-02>.
- [22] E. Henshin. “The Eclipse Foundation (2013)”. In: URL <http://www.eclipse.org/-modeling/emft/henshin/> ().
- [23] S. Khaitan, Q. Lin, and J. M. Dolan. “Safe Planning and Control Under Uncertainty for Self-Driving”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* 70.10 (2021), pp. 9826–9837. DOI: [10.1109/TVT.2021.3108525](https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2021.3108525).
- [24] M. Kwiatkowska, G. Norman, and D. Parker. “PRISM: Probabilistic symbolic model checker”. In: *International Conference on Modelling Techniques and Tools for Computer Performance Evaluation*. Springer. 2002, pp. 200–204.
- [25] G. Lee and J. Jung. “Decentralized Platoon Join-in-Middle Protocol Considering Communication Delay for Connected and Automated Vehicle”. In: *Sensors* 21.21 (2021), p. 7126. DOI: [10.3390/s21217126](https://doi.org/10.3390/s21217126).
- [26] M. Lushpenko, N. Ferry, H. Song, F. Chauvel, and A. Solberg. “Using Adaptation Plans to Control the Behavior of Models@ runtime.” In: *Models@ run. time*. 2015, pp. 11–20.
- [27] M. Maximova, H. Giese, and C. Krause. “Probabilistic Timed Graph Transformation Systems”. In: *Graph Transformation - 10th International Conference, ICGT 2017, Held as Part of STAF 2017, Marburg, Germany, July 18-19, 2017, Proceedings*. Ed. by J. de Lara and D. Plump. Vol. 10373. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2017, pp. 159–175. ISBN: 978-3-319-61469-4. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-61470-0_10](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-61470-0_10).

- [28] M. Maximova, H. Giese, and C. Krause. “Probabilistic timed graph transformation systems”. In: *J. Log. Algebr. Meth. Program.* 101 (2018), pp. 110–131. DOI: [10.1016/j.jlamp.2018.09.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlamp.2018.09.003).
- [29] M. Maximova, S. Schneider, and H. Giese. “Compositional Analysis of Probabilistic Timed Graph Transformation Systems”. In: *Formal Aspects Comput.* 35.3 (2023), 16:1–16:79. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3572782>.
- [30] M. Maximova, S. Schneider, and H. Giese. “Interval Probabilistic Timed Graph Transformation Systems”. In: *ICGT 2021*. Ed. by F. Gadducci and T. Kehrer. Vol. 12741. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2021, pp. 221–239. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-78946-6_12](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78946-6_12).
- [31] G. A. Moreno, J. Cámara, D. Garlan, and B. R. Schmerl. “Proactive self-adaptation under uncertainty: a probabilistic model checking approach”. In: *ESEC/FSE 2015*. Ed. by E. D. Nitto, M. Harman, and P. Heymans. ACM, 2015, pp. 1–12. DOI: [10.1145/2786805.2786853](https://doi.org/10.1145/2786805.2786853).
- [32] S. Neumann. “Modellierung und Verifikation zeitbehafteter Graphtransformationssysteme mittels GROOVE”. Master’s thesis, University of Paderborn, 2007.
- [33] S. Neumann. “Modellierung und Verifikation zeitbehafteter Graphtransformationssysteme mittels GROOVE”. MA thesis. University of Paderborn, 2007.
- [34] M. M. Quottrup, T. Bak, and R. Zamanabadi. “Multi-robot planning: A timed automata approach”. In: *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, 2004. Proceedings. ICRA ’04. 2004*. Vol. 5. IEEE, 2004, pp. 4417–4422.
- [35] S. Schneider, M. Maximova, L. Sakizoglou, and H. Giese. “Formal testing of timed graph transformation systems using metric temporal graph logic”. In: *Int. J. Softw. Tools Technol. Transf.* 23.3 (2021), pp. 411–488. DOI: [10.1007/s10009-020-00585-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10009-020-00585-w).
- [36] D. Shin and K. Yi. “Compensation of wireless communication delay for integrated risk management of automated vehicle”. In: *2015 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, IV 2015, Seoul, South Korea, June 28 - July 1, 2015*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 1355–1360. DOI: [10.1109/IVS.2015.7225904](https://doi.org/10.1109/IVS.2015.7225904).
- [37] B. I. Silva and B. H. Krogh. “Modeling and verification of hybrid systems with clocked and unclocked events”. In: *CDC 2001*. IEEE, 2001, pp. 762–767. DOI: [10.1109/.2001.980198](https://doi.org/10.1109/.2001.980198).
- [38] M. Tichy and B. Klöpper. “Planning self-adaption with graph transformations”. In: *AGTIVE 2011, Revised Selected and Invited Papers*. Springer, 2012, pp. 137–152.
- [39] Y. Tsuchie and T. Ushio. “Control-invariance of Sampleddata Hybrid Systems with periodically Clocked Events and jitter”. In: *ADHS 2006*. Ed. by C. G. Cassandras, A. Giua, C. Seatzu, and J. Zaytoon. Vol. 39. IFAC Proceedings Volumes 5. Elsevier, 2006, pp. 417–422. DOI: [10.3182/20060607-3-IT-3902.00075](https://doi.org/10.3182/20060607-3-IT-3902.00075).
- [40] M. Van Steen and A. S. Tanenbaum. “A brief introduction to distributed systems”. In: *Computing* 98 (2016), pp. 967–1009.
- [41] D. Weyns, H. V. D. Parunak, F. Michel, T. Holvoet, and J. Ferber. “Environments for Multiagent Systems State-of-the-Art and Research Challenges”. In: *E4MAS 2004, Revised Selected Papers*. Ed. by D. Weyns, H. V. D. Parunak, and F. Michel. Vol. 3374. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2004, pp. 1–47. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-540-32259-7_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-32259-7_1).
- [42] H. Xu, S. Schneider, and H. Giese. “Integrating Look-ahead Design-time and Run-time Control-synthesis for Graph Transformation Systems”. In: *FASE 2024, ETAPS 2024. Proceedings*. Ed. by D. Beyer and A. Cavalcanti. (accepted). 2024.

- [43] R. Zhang, K. Cai, Y. Gan, and W. M. Wonham. “Delay-robustness in distributed control of timed discrete-event systems based on supervisor localisation”. In: *Int. J. Control* 89.10 (2016), pp. 2055–2072. DOI: [10.1080/00207179.2016.1147606](https://doi.org/10.1080/00207179.2016.1147606).